

Research Article

Investigation of the Activities Performed by Experimental Researchers in a Software Engineering Lab Using an Ethnographic Methodology

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Context: Replication plays a critical role in building cumulative scientific knowledge. However, in the context of Empirical Software Engineering (ESE), replication efforts face persistent difficulties, both technical and methodological, which hinder reproducibility and generalizability. We explored whether the problems were due to formal issues, such as under-specification or miscommunication, or intrinsic reasons, i.e., the existing replication procedures may not meet the researchers' needs.

Objective: To understand how ESE researchers conduct experiments in real-world settings.

Method: We conducted an ethnographic study with an experimental software engineering group, using interviews, observations, and analysis of internal documentation.

Results: We have created conceptual and process models representing experimentation, replication, and synthesis in the target research group. These models align with mainstream procedures at a high level but often break down in practice during specialized tasks such as coordination or documentation. The experimental process observed in the group differs from common assumptions and textbook descriptions in terms of (1) the number and diversity of activities involved, (2) the presence of differentiated roles, (3) the granularity of conceptual elements, and (4) the varying perspectives across subareas or families of experiments.

Conclusions: The discrepancies between actual laboratory practices and idealized process models may hinder knowledge transfer and complicate replication. We plan to extend this research by involving additional research groups, for instance, through surveys, to examine the generalizability of our findings.

1. Introduction

Replication is generally troublesome [1], particularly in the social and life sciences [2, 3]. In Empirical Software Engineering (ESE¹), there is a consensus that replications are important [4], but the number of replications is small [5], and the rate of confirmation of previous results is limited [6].

Several reasons prevent replication. These have been discussed in prior works, e.g., [7–11]. In this paper, we focus on a potential cause that, to our knowledge, has not been explored so far: how ESE researchers conduct experimentation in practice.

Informal evidence, including conversations with peers, article reviews, and direct observation, suggests that researchers may follow distinct experimental processes, i.e., activities to execute experiments in ESE. While experiment reports tend to look relatively uniform due to reporting guidelines [12, 13], the underlying data generation processes often differ considerably.

This paper aims to investigate how experimental researchers conduct experiments in practice. We intend to find out how experimental researchers plan, execute, analyze, and report their investigations and what concepts, protocols, and processes they use.

We applied an ethnographic method [14, 15] within an experienced experimental research group. We observed the researchers in their laboratory for 2 years. We created conceptual and process models to represent the concepts they use and the daily activities they perform. These models fit the community's procedures and terminology at a high level. Still, the models show the following particularities at lower levels: (1) The number and diversity of activities, (2) the existence of different roles, (3) the granularity of the concepts used by the roles, and (4) the viewpoints that different subareas or families of experiments have about the overall process.

The contributions of this paper are as follows:

- Identifying activities that depart from or are not described in mainstream experimentation procedures.
- Characterizing roles, i.e., groups of experimental activities performed by the same person, in ESE research.
- Evidence of the existence of tacit knowledge in ESE, which, in turn, leads to discrepancies between experimentation protocols and actual practice.
- Conceptual and process models that represent how experimentation is conducted *in practice* in an experimental research group.

Finally, we wish to open a discussion in the ESE community:

- Should those differential characteristics in experimentation in software engineering (SE) be disregarded as inherently contextual?
- Alternatively: Are they more common than they may seem, so they should be further investigated and eventually integrated into mainstream practice?

The remainder of the article is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the research method. Section 3 reports the stages of the ethnographic research and the observations made. Section 4 reports the concept and process models. Section 5 discusses the results and the connections with the existing literature. Section 6 details the threats to validity and the related mitigation strategies. Finally, in Section 7, we present the conclusions and future work.

2. Research Method

Ethnography is a *participant observation* method used with some frequency in SE, e.g., [16–19]. It does not interfere (beyond the ethnographic researchers' presence) with the observed ESE researchers' "life" [14]. Ethnographic researchers adopt "the ESE researchers' point of view" to better understand the reason for their actions [20, pp. 55–56]. Thus, the biases and misperceptions that ESE researchers might have about themselves can be detected. Ethnography also captures the rich context that surrounds ESE researchers.

Ethnography identifies details that are ignored by other methodologies, including Artificial Intelligence [21]. The disadvantage is the time required for learning [14]. Thus, we opted to study a single experimental research group over a long

period, rather than working with several experimental research groups over shorter periods. This decision was also motivated by the challenge of finding several open-minded experimental research groups willing to participate in this research. We selected a representative, i.e., respected and well-known, research group to guarantee (to the extent possible) the reliability of the results, their validity, and the findings' scientific significance [22].

We followed Runenson et al.'s case study guidelines [23] wherever they apply to ethnographical studies. Our research protocol is organized along three axes:

- Context selection, i.e., selection of an experimental research group that facilitated the study under optimal conditions.
- Data collection procedures.
- Data analysis procedures.

To avoid confusion, we referred to the "ESE researchers" with whom we interacted during the investigation as "the experimenters." We referred to ourselves, the authors, as "the researchers." We, authors/researchers, play two different roles in the investigation:

- Efraín R. Fonseca C. and Edison G. Espinosa conducted the ethnographic study as part of their Ph.D. Edison G. Espinosa abandoned the ethnographic study early (during the investigation reported in Section 3.2) and changed the orientation of his Ph.D. This is the reason he is not authoring this paper. The personal opinions poured in Section 3 belong to these two researchers, particularly Efraín R. Fonseca C.
- Oscar Dieste and Natalia Juristo supervised the investigation. Their views and opinions are not reflected in this manuscript.

2.1. Context Selection. We considered an experimental research group "representative" if it fulfilled the following selection criteria:

- The experimental research group has extensive experience in ESE research.
- The ESE community recognizes the experimenters as specialists in their areas.
- The group has numerous publications in reputable journals and maintains internal documentation, thereby establishing a verifiable track record.
- One of the main drivers of this research is to explore the connection between replication and laboratory practices. We positively value the fact that the experimental research group conducts replications or families of experiments.

Based on these criteria, we selected an experimental research group with over 20 years of experience in SE experimentation. The experimenters have a long-standing track record of publication in reputable journals and conferences.

TABLE 1: Techniques and tools for information acquisition, by source.

Source	Technique	Instruments
Experimenters knowledge	Interviews	Video camera, paper, pencil
	Focus groups	Video camera, blackboard, cardboard, board markers, chalkboard eraser, etc
	Process modeling	Video camera, paper, pencil
	Instrumental systems	Email, videoconferences, internet
Common literature	Experience-based learning	Literature review, review of experimental material, experimentation in practice
	Documentation analysis	Comprehensive reading of literature, reading summaries, software support tools
Experimental material	Documentation analysis	Systematic analysis of experimental material, trials with data
Group activities	Participatory observation	Literature review, researchers knowledge

The group has focused on replications and families of experiments since they consider that isolated experiments do not contribute significantly to scientific knowledge. The manuscript conceals the group's identity, but it is disclosed in the raw data repository (see Section 2.4).

2.2. Data Collection Procedures. The information sources within the experimental research group under study (RGUS) are as follows:

- Experimenters' knowledge.
- General and specific literature, e.g., the book "Experimentation in Software Engineering" [24].
- General and specific experimental materials, e.g., experimental designs.
- Periodic and/or *ad-hoc* activities carried out, e.g., experimental planning.

These procedures included interviews, focus groups, participatory observation, and document analysis, as summarized in Table 1.

Ethnographic information gathering is characterized by being cyclical, iterative, and incremental. The data acquisition process was based on a taxonomy of information-gathering techniques, categorized according to the level of contact with the primary source of information. Such a taxonomy proposes three levels of information gathering: direct participation with the source (level 1), indirect participation with the source (level 2), and study of the experiment material without the involvement of the source (level 3) [25]. Table 1 describes the information-gathering techniques and instruments and the corresponding information sources to which they can be applied.

The order in which the researchers contacted information sources was not fixed. The frequency of contact depended on the researchers' need to answer research questions during the ethnographic research and the availability of each source.

2.3. Data Analysis Procedure. The ethnographic practice involves storing the raw data and then interpreting the findings [26]. In this research, the data analysis procedure consisted of four activities:

- Preparation of materials: The information sources are classified and categorized so experimenters and researchers can manage them.
- Information acquisition: While analyzing the information sources, researchers gradually acquire basic knowledge about experimentation, which helps them understand the experimenters' knowledge and behavior more easily.
- Verification of information: This is probably the most complex activity. The knowledge obtained from the sources complemented each other. We used triangulation to explain the findings and identify new areas of inquiry. All findings were discussed with the experimenters to avoid misunderstandings and verify that the resulting activities aligned with those they carried out in practice.
- Generation of results: Finally, we obtained the results as final products after several iterations of comparison, verification, and consensus between researchers and experimenters. The expected results will be models (conceptual and process) and practices derived from the interviews with the experimenters.

2.4. Research Documentation. The raw data obtained in this study were organized as shown in Figure 1. The tree represents a repository of around 20 GB of information. The repository contains pictures, recordings, models, reports, and transcriptions, most of which are in Spanish (the operational language used during the research). Spanish is widespread enough to utilize the repository with little effort. The final products, such as models, have been translated into English to enhance the reader's understanding. The repository is not public because it contains personal data. However, upon request, the corresponding author will share the repository with interested researchers.

Since this study is grounded in ethnographic observation and not in experimental manipulation or statistical modeling, traditional quantitative validity measures do not apply. Instead, we ensured the trustworthiness of our findings through the use of qualitative validation strategies. These included observation

FIGURE 1: Repository structure. For instance, interviews were conducted using video recordings and paper notes, while focus groups made use of boards, markers, and erasers, as detailed in Table 1.

saturation (where no new relevant behaviors emerged after repeated sessions), triangulation with relevant literature, and informal member checking through discussions with participants during the observation period.

3. Ethnographic Study

We present the results of the ethnographic study in chronological order. First, we describe the analysis of the RGUS's preferred literature sources and review the RGUS's specific experimental material. Later, we comment on our experiences replicating an existing experiment. Finally, we describe how we formalized the information into concept and process models using interviews, focus groups, and workshops.

3.1. First Approximation. In the first stages of the investigation, the researchers did not have an ethnographic methodology in mind, but rather something less demanding, in line with existing qualitative studies, e.g., [27–31]. They initially conducted interviews to clarify RGUS knowledge and convert it directly into models.

The interviews with RGUS members provided only limited publicly available knowledge about experimentation. The experimenters believed that interviews were unnecessary because researchers could acquire the required knowledge by studying the literature they considered standard (e.g., [32]). Despite their reservations, we conducted a first round of interviews, but the communication barriers and missing experimental materials limited their usefulness. This experience later motivated us to adopt a more immersive ethnographic approach and, subsequently, a second round of semi-structured interviews.

However, communication became problematic as the interviews progressed into specialized areas, such as specific

families of experiments. For instance, the experimenters supported their explanations using specific experimental materials that the researchers did not possess. The researchers were also initially unsure how to interpret the experimenters' discussions. At this point, the need for a different research methodology—ethnography—became apparent. Consequently, the researchers adopted a slower, more immersive approach. They conducted additional activities to become familiar with the standard literature and experimental materials. The interaction with the experimenters also evolved: initially, the researchers participated as experimental subjects and later became team members in one of the RGUS families of experiments.

3.1.1. Analysis of the Relevant Literature. The experimenters used the books by Wohlin et al. [32] and Juristo and Moreno [33] as primary sources for their experimentation process. They also referred to specific papers that advised how to experiment in SE, e.g., Basili et al. [34], and Kitchenham et al. [35]. Basili et al.'s work [36] was also considered relevant due to the experimenters' interest in carrying out experimental replications.

We reviewed the literature in depth and noticed that the sources did not use coherent terminology. Initially, it appeared to us that the literature described various experimental procedures. We later verified that the different terms referred to essentially the same activities, such as:

- Wohlin et al. [32]: “Experiment idea, Experiment scoping, Experiment planning, Experiment operation, Analysis & interpretation, Presentation & package, and Experiment report.”
- Juristo and Moreno [33]: “Objective Definition, Design, Execution, and Analysis.”

- Basili et al. [34]: “Definition, Planning, Operation, and Interpretation.”
- Kitchenham et al. [35]: “Experimental context, Experimental design, Conduct of the experiment and Data Collection, Analysis, Presentation of results, and Interpretation of results.”

We searched for additional ESE books to determine whether terminological diversity was a widespread issue. We found a new edition of Wohlin et al.’s book [24] and the specialized books by Runeson et al. [23] and Kitchenham et al. [37]. As expected, these books shared standard terms but used varied terminology throughout the text, contributing to the observed diversity.

3.1.2. Review of Experimental Material. The RGUS’ experimental materials were a valuable source of information, as they represented nearly two decades of experimental work and reflected the tacit knowledge [38] embedded in the group. However, accessing these materials proved challenging due to their scattered and disorganized state. We required the experimenters’ assistance to locate specific documents or data files, interpret their structure and content, and obtain access to related materials. The experimental materials evolved over time. Experiments varied significantly in documentary support, regardless of their date. The experimental family explained the differences more strongly than the timeline; materials related to different families of experiments showed significant differences—for instance, digital raw data versus handwritten papers or automatic tools for variable measurement versus manual tools.

Concerning the experimental process, all experimental materials generally describe the activities carried out. However, the execution order and the relationships between activities remained unclear and depended heavily on the experimenters’ tacit knowledge. Terminological diversity also affected the materials, especially across different families of experiments.

We intended to reflect RGUS knowledge in process and conceptual models. However, we largely failed to consolidate the terminology, resulting in a relatively simple model (see this link). Still, this abstract preliminary model was satisfactory for continuing the ethnographic research.

3.2. Becoming Active Participants. The concepts the researchers had acquired were still uncertain. We needed external confirmation. Thus, we applied the learn-by-doing methodology [39] to verify whether our understanding was correct by conducting an experiment ourselves.

3.2.1. Experiment Selection. Instead of designing an experiment from scratch, the researchers replicated one that the RGUS had previously conducted. The replication was later published elsewhere.

Replicating the experimenters’ previous work drew their attention and ensured their collaboration. Moreover, it enabled us to recreate the design, execution, analysis, and reporting of an experiment that we had previously studied only through its documentation. Ultimately, the replication helped us understand the experimenters’ motivations and decision-making more thoroughly.

3.2.2. Replication Planning. Several challenges hindered the replication [7, 8, 12, 40–42], the most important being the lack of a detailed description of the experimental activities. These included how to approach the experimental design, what experimental objects were required, and the order in which they should be used. To address these gaps, we requested the cooperation of the experimenters who had run the baseline experiment, so we could schedule the experimental activities and adapt the design to the new context.

3.2.3. Conduction. Efraín R. Fonseca C. conducted a literal replication [42] in an academic setting external to the RGUS. The availability of explicit experimental materials, such as questionnaires, task descriptions, and programs, greatly facilitated the replication. These materials had predefined all relevant aspects in advance. Measurement was the most complex and controversial aspect. For instance, experimental subjects returned test cases, which were manually interpreted rather than executed. We again required the experimenters’ cooperation to complete the measurement. Although the measurement procedure initially seemed controversial, it became fully understandable after discussion. We learned that experimental protocols depend on the specific experimental task, which in turn depends on the research area. The remaining steps—such as calculating measurements from raw data and formatting—were straightforward and did not involve any uncertainty. It was possible to reproduce the duplicate files used in the baseline experiment.

3.2.4. Analysis and Reporting. We sought help to analyze and report the replication because we lacked statistical training. In retrospect, both the analysis and the reporting turned out to be relatively straightforward, as the experimental design used (*crossover*) was linked to a well-established analysis method [43]. Moreover, we followed available reporting guidelines [12]. The experimenters confirmed that the analysis and reporting of experiments generally did not involve significant SE-specific challenges.

The differences observed between the replication and the baseline experiment supported our belief that, at least for the RGUS, clear guidelines for literal, external, and independent replication [42] were lacking—regardless of whether incidents occurred during the replication. As a result, the original experimenters’ involvement was essential to compare the results from the baseline and the replication.

3.2.5. Assessment. In retrospect, the replication was the key to clarifying the RGUS’s experimental process. The replication exercise enhanced our understanding and enabled the verification of previous findings, such as the terminology used by the RGUS. We also uncovered new insights, including the specificity of experimental protocols and, notably, the presence of extensive tacit knowledge.

3.3. Modeling the RGUS’ Knowledge. After completing the experiment, we were unsure of how to proceed. The investigation had been operationally successful, except for the analysis phase, which required specific statistical expertise. We had satisfactorily completed all other activities. The models had improved during the replication (see this link), and to the best of our knowledge, we had not overlooked anything relevant.

FIGURE 2: Example of a sketch made by the experimenters. The researchers have used drafts like this to progress in the definition of the experimental process workflow described in Section 4.1.

Nonetheless, we were not entirely satisfied with the ethnographic study. We had replicated **one** experiment in **one** specific SE area. However, nothing ensured that we would not require the experimenters' assistance in a hypothetical future replication [42, 44]. The persistence of tacit knowledge represented a serious threat to validity.

3.3.1. Semi-Structured Interviews. We decided to conduct a new series of semi-structured interviews with the experimenters. The key difference from the first approximation was our decision to focus not on the SE experimental process *in general* but on replicating *specific families of experiments*. Based on the experience acquired during the replication, we believed this strategy could help reveal the experimenters' tacit knowledge.

We designed an open-ended questionnaire to encourage the experimenters to provide a spontaneous yet relatively structured account of their experiences. Instead of taking notes, we recorded the interviews on video to capture body language as well. Additionally, we collected paper sketches (e.g., see Figure 2) that some experimenters used to support their narratives. We analyzed the videos and sketches using protocol analysis [45, 46]. We produced a report after each interview (see this link).

The process was smooth, as each experimenter provided a coherent narrative. We conducted a total of seven interviews with six RGUS members. Each time, we refined the knowledge we had acquired. The reader can check the models' evolution through this link. When the progress was marginal, the interviews concluded.

3.3.2. Preliminary Models. We developed process and concept models, along with a workflow to represent the relationships between activities identified during the investigation. We presented only the main characteristics of these models here, as the ethnographic research was still ongoing at that point. The models and workflow still require validation by the experimenters. Full details are provided in Section 4.

- **Preliminary experimental process model (EPM):** We realized that the RGUS conducted experiments resembling the structured processes found in SE, such as ISO/IEC 12,207 [47]. Ultimately, all of them could be abstracted as processes. We therefore identified six high-level experimental processes: support, generation of pieces of knowledge, publication, synthesis, basic, and organization. Each process comprised several associated activities. For instance, the *basic process* included the following: pre-execution (context adaptation, experiment redesign, and experiment design), execution (presession, in-session, and post-session), and post-execution (raw data generation, data processing, data analysis, and data interpretation) (see this link).
- **Preliminary workflow:** It illustrated the connections between experimental processes (see this link). According to the experimenters, the experimental process involved three main stages or paths: experimentation, replication, and synthesis. The activities performed in each stage were classified according to the EPM described above. Experimenters did not usually perform all activities, although they typically knew how to do them, even if not flawlessly. Conversely, different responsibilities were often assigned to the same experimenter. We identified the following roles, whose names reflected their primary responsibilities: (1) *Research Manager (RM)*, (2) *Experiment Manager (EM)*, and (3) *Senior Experimenter (SrEx)*. These roles were in charge of (1) planning the experimental research, (2) managing logistics, and (3) conducting the experiment in practice, respectively. The study revealed overlapping responsibilities among roles, such as domain and topic selection.
- **Preliminary conceptual model:** The preliminary results at the conceptual model level revealed activities similar to those described in the literature, indicating that this model evolved the least (see this link).

3.3.3. Double-Checking Using Focus Groups. Interviews had limitations for eliciting tacit knowledge. Once the preliminary models were ready, we presented them to all RGUS experimenters for double-checking.

As mentioned above, we had organized the semi-structured interviews around families of experiments. It turned out to be a fortunate mistake. The families of experiments were relatively homogeneous. The experimenters involved in each family quickly agreed and provided a coherent picture of the experimental process. However, experimenters from different families disagreed on many aspects,

particularly the specific arrangements used in their experimental families.

We intended to solve the disagreements using a consensus-reaching technique, e.g., DELPHI [48]. However, social pressure did not emerge as an issue. We therefore organized focus groups. The most SrEx acted as a moderator, but only to keep the discussion on track. The researchers merely observed. Each session lasted at least 2 h. Before the focus groups, the experimenters reviewed the concept models. We began with these models because they were more straightforward and smaller. The process models/workflow were later updated based on the changes made to the concept models.

The focus groups triggered substantial growth in the models' detail, following heated discussions that reaffirmed the presence of terminological diversity *even among experimenters who carried out similar activities within the same family of experiments*. A likely explanation is the type of training each experimenter received. Referring to "training" in the context of RGUS may be inaccurate, as most of its members were self-taught, with few exceptions. The preferred SE experimental literature, e.g., [49, 50], did not shape their learning process. Few of these resources existed when the experimenters began their careers. They selected materials based on their individual preferences and the experimental families in which they were involved. As a result, terminological diversity naturally followed.

The experimenters did not reach a consensus during the focus group sessions. Discussions among experimenters from different families followed a circular pattern: one experimenter proposed a change that another later reversed. Substantial agreement emerged only *within each family of experiments*. The progress we had achieved during the replication phase of the ethnographic study (see Section 3.2) was possible because we focused on concrete families of experiments—a factor we had entirely overlooked at the time.

The concept model we obtained at this stage is available at this link. The agreement achieved among experimenters is evident in the model's structure and content.

3.3.4. Role-Focused Workshops. We did not aim to explore SE family-specific experimental processes in depth. Although potentially valuable, we considered it more suitable for future research. Given the limited time available for the Ph.D., we focused on improving the models by shifting the perspective from experimental family to *experimental role*. While we had no initial reason to believe that roles would foster agreement, we decided to test the idea. We continued to use the concept model to guide the focus groups, rather than the process models, since roles are tied to activities rather than concepts. Activities appeared more uniform across experimenters than concepts, making the approach promising.

The strategy was simple. Experimenters who had performed the same role gathered informally and discussed only the tasks associated with that role. The meetings were peaceful, unlike the more intense focus group sessions, and the conversations were constructive. Setting aside family-specific issues, we double-checked the existence of roles. The experimenters agreed that these roles made sense, even though they had not previously perceived their responsibilities in these terms.

FIGURE 3: Relationships between the *experimental process workflow* (top) and the *experimental process model* (down). This model reflects the practices observed in the RGUS group and is not intended to be prescriptive.

We also broke down the conceptual model into role-specific conceptual models. These represented groups of concepts that the experimenters used when performing a specific role. Most experimental activities were role-specific; for example, the senior experimenter role used the run-kit concept exclusively. The role-specific conceptual models are available through these links: 1, 2, 3.

4. Results

The ethnographic research yielded the following three main results: (1) an *experimental process workflow* (EPW), (2) an *experimental research concept model*, and, to a lesser extent,

(3) an EPM. We describe them below. We did not use standard notations (e.g., UML or BPMN) because experimental researchers (and probably readers) have different ages, backgrounds, and careers. We prioritized communication over model formality.

4.1. EPW. The so-called EPW represented the tasks carried out during SE experimentation (from the RGUS' perspective) and their logical sequence. The workflow is available at this link and, at lower resolution, is shown in Figure 3.

The EPW model showed three well-defined paths corresponding to the key SE experimental research processes: (1) experimentation (purple), (2) replication (green), and

(3) synthesis (yellow). Based on the existence (or non-existence) of new moderator variables and the new knowledge generated in the last round, there were also analysis activities associated with planning new cycles of experimentation, replication, or synthesis, as well as reporting related to the publication of results (highlighted in blue). These processes appeared to be associated with the experimentation and synthesis paths.

4.1.1. Experimentation Path. Experimentation is the heart of experimental research since replication and synthesis stem from it. However, in some circumstances, experimentation may require the prior execution of synthesis (e.g., when selecting the experiment's topic) or replication (e.g., in adapting to the context) activities. According to the experimenters, the experimentation activities are as follows:

- Selecting the experiment domain.
- Selecting the experiment topic.
- Selecting the experimental hypothesis.
- Planning the experiment.
- Creating the experimental kit.
- Executing and post-execution of the experiment.

When the experiment results do not meet the experimenters' expectations, they plan a new cycle of experimental research by redesigning and conducting the experiment again. This redesign activity usually happens when investigating fundamental topics. Its duration varies depending on the complexity of the topic. Still, it often involves multiple iterations across several weeks or even months, especially when methodological adjustments and consensus-building among experimenters are required.

This divergence between the planned protocol and the enacted behaviors was particularly evident during the coordination phase. Although the official plan prescribed independent task execution based on prior assignments, the observed researchers frequently relied on ad hoc discussions, unplanned negotiations, and informal agreements. These practices often deviated from the expected protocol and revealed how actual coordination needs overrode the initial model.

4.1.2. Replication Path. Replication is the practice on which scientific knowledge is based, hand in hand with the synthesis of results [51]. The RGUS agrees that replication is essential for experimental research, explicitly (RGUS experimenters claim that) and, more importantly, implicitly (the experimental workflow contains minute details about replication activities). The replication path consists of the following activities:

- Definition of replication,
- Study and update the experimental kit,
- Adaptation to the context, and
- Creation of operational elements.

4.1.3. Synthesis Path. According to the RGUS experimenters, results can be synthesized from systematic literature reviews, systematic mapping studies, or experiments sharing a common

goal (a family of experiments). In each case, the experimenters apply particular synthesis techniques (e.g., aggregated or individual patient meta-analysis) and interpret the results. During the interpretation, the researchers can identify moderator variables or generalize pieces of knowledge. Such findings may lead to reforming the synthesis's goals or conducting a new cycle of experimental research. In addition, experimenters generally publish results after a synthesis, in conjunction with planning the next round.

The information obtained from the RGUS is quite general and in line with the community's understanding of synthesis. That is expected. Our findings are predictable because the RGUS lacked experimenters with the required expert knowledge during this research. On the other hand, the limited insight into synthesis represents an indirect confirmation of the success of the ethnographic research. Our understanding is proportional to the expert knowledge available, and there is considerable specialized knowledge on the RGUS regarding experimentation and replication, which was our primary goal.

4.2. Experimental Research Concept Model. This research's conceptual model is not monolithic; on the contrary, it is composed of three submodels (more accurately, viewpoints) aligned with prominent experimental roles: RM, EM, and SrEx. These roles reflect the division of responsibilities observed in the EPW. The experimenters used the best-known generic phases of the experimentation process to develop new versions of the conceptual model, starting from version eight, which was generated during the first interview phase (see link).

4.2.1. RM Viewpoint. The RM viewpoint is available at this link. The RM is associated with the following responsibilities:

- During the experiment definition phase, the RM manages the "problem definition" and the "hypothesis definition."
- In the experiment design phase, the RM is responsible for "human resource management," which includes individuals who could "run," "replicate," or be interested in "replicating" the experiment. The RM also receives information about the "Expected results," "execution context," and "new variables of interest."
- While the experiment is running, the RM monitors events, although the data acquisition phase remains transparent to them.
- In the data analysis phase, the RM becomes aware of the "analysis results" and contributes to identifying the "findings," preparing "publications," and articulating "pieces of knowledge."

4.2.2. EM Viewpoint. The EM viewpoint is available at this link. The EM is associated with the following responsibilities:

- In the experiment definition phase, the EM actively interacts with all experiment entities, alongside the SrEx. However, the EM plays an observational role in the "hypothesis definition."

- During the experiment design phase, the EM focuses on improving the “experiment guides” related to “instruments,” “objects,” and the “experimental kit.” The EM also analyzes the context in which the experiment will occur.
- Throughout the execution and data acquisition phases, the EM does not lose sight of the “events” that arise and could affect the results. The EM also analyzes the “correctness” of the “collected items” and the consistency of “raw data.”
- In the data analysis phase, the EM contributes to the “re-analysis” in search of new “variables of interest” to the RGUS. Additionally, the EM can observe the analysis results to suggest findings that could be useful in publications.

4.2.3. *SrEx Viewpoint.* The SrEx viewpoint is available at this link. The perspective is as follows:

- In the experiment definition phase, the SrEx observes the “experiment definition,” hypotheses’ levels,” and “metrics” in the first phase of the experimental investigation. The SrEx participates in defining the “hypothesis,” “factors,” and “response variable.”
- In the experimental design phase, the SrEx interacts with a large number of entities; hence, it is necessary to divide such a phase into three subphases for this role: *experimental operation design*, *experiment design*, and *artifact generation*.
 - During the *experimental operation design*, the SrEx defines the “experimental objects” for each “experimental task,” considering the minute details of each experimental object’s characteristics.
 - During the *experiment design*, proper, the SrEx establishes the execution context’s “parameters,” the “design type” with its “groups” and assigned “experimental subjects,” the “levels” defined and their combination per “session” and “period,” “experimental instruments,” and the “measurement procedure.”
 - Finally, in the *artifact generation*, the SrEx fundamentally develops the “run-kit,” which includes the construction of instances of “guides,” “experimental instruments,” and “experimental objects.” Such “instances” are the tools that the “subjects” need to participate in the “experiment.”
- While the experiment is running, the SrEx records all events produced to analyze their impact on the experiment results.
- During data acquisition, the SrEx records the resulting collected items, creates the raw data, and obtains measurements.
- Finally, in the data analysis phase, the SrEx performs the analysis, obtains the findings, and prepares the publications with the help of the RM and EM.

4.3. *EPM.* The workflow and conceptual models represent the experimental research process carried out in the RGUS. Other experimental research groups may follow different approaches. We have created an initial, generic (i.e., generally applicable) EPM with the help of the most experienced experimenter at RGUS. The model was inspired by the software life cycle [47]. We have adapted the concepts from ISO/IEC 12207 to the SE experimentation domain. Most items were taken from the EPW (see Figure 3), while a smaller portion derives from the conceptual models. The complete process model can be accessed at this link.

The EPM contains six groups of processes that define the SE experimental research life cycle: (1) the Basic process, (2) the Support process, (3) the Knowledge item generation process, (4) the Publication process, (5) the Synthesis process, and (6) the Organizational process.

4.3.1. *Basic Process.* The basic process involves fundamental activities performed by the experimenters in their RM, SrEx, and EM roles before, during, and after conducting an experiment. Before the experiment, the activities focus on their design, e.g., adapting the experiment to the research context. During the experiment, experimenters pay attention to events that occur before, during, and after the execution of the experiment’s session. After execution, the activities focus on data-related tasks, such as generating raw data and conducting data analysis.

4.3.2. *Support Process.* The support process includes activities carried out by the EM to manage artifacts and assist those interested in performing replications. These activities include the following:

- The management of materials before the experiment’s execution (e.g., experiment design document),
- The materials used during the experiment (e.g., templates for data collection),
- The materials obtained at the end of the experiment (e.g., filled templates and subjects’ code), and
- Knowledge transference as a support style during replication activities.

4.3.3. *Knowledge Items Generation Process.* The knowledge items generation process consolidates the activities performed by the RM to manage the knowledge acquired after each experiment, e.g., the knowledge generated in each experimentation phase, the knowledge transferred to professionals, or the knowledge generated during the identification of moderator variables.

4.3.4. *Publications Process.* This group of activities focuses on reporting the experiment findings (led by the SrEx), aggregation of results (by the EM), and experimentation goals (by the RM).

4.3.5. *Synthesis Process.* The EM carries out the synthesis processes. Different types of synthesis have varying evidential

levels, such as meta-analysis, re-analysis, and informal aggregation.

4.3.6. Organizational Process. The organizational process encompasses RM's management activities throughout the SE experimental research cycle, including human resources and publications management. Likewise, the EM also performs management activities on the experimental materials. Finally, some activities related to synthesis management have not been assigned to any role yet.

Figure 3 shows a not-very-good coincidence between the activities of the EPW and those of the EPM since, as indicated before, each model has its purpose; still, we found several relationships.

This model is plausible, but based solely on the RGUS' perspective. Further research (in this regard, see Section 7) is necessary to ensure that the model represents the experimental SE community's experimental process.

5. Discussion and Related Work

This research aims to find out how experimenters work in practice. After conducting the ethnographic research, we obtained models (process, workflow, and conceptual). The conceptual model connects with empirical researchers' "prominent picture" of their research area. The process and workflow models represent a novel contribution; to our knowledge, such detailed descriptions of the experimental process are unavailable in the existing literature.

The models described in Section 4 are available in full detail online. In this section, we would like to focus on some interesting model features:

- The experimental process is broader than we usually recognize as "experimentation." An experiment can be characterized as a small (or not that small) research project. It includes activities related to (see this link):
 - management (resources, research lines, among others),
 - negotiation (e.g., with companies),
 - document/artifact support,
 - publication, among others.

Although all empirical researchers know these activities, it is surprising that they are seldom mentioned (if ever) in ESE literature. To the best of our knowledge, reference texts, e.g., [32, 33], do not address these activities beyond marginal notes. Such richness in the number and diversity of activities raises obvious consequences in experimental education and training.

- The ethnographic study revealed one consequence of such diversity. It is possible, albeit unlikely, that one experimenter performs all experimental activities. These activities are not only complex: they demand time. In a project (research or not), the diversity of activities is usually associated with roles with well-defined responsibilities. Also in experimentation. We identified three roles: (1) *RM*, (2) *EM*, and (3) *SrEx*. These roles are probably related to the RGUS' size; smaller (or larger)

groups may have more generic/specialized roles. The concept of "role" applied to experimentation is unusual but not entirely new. Mohamed et al. [52] proposed a framework to conduct ESE experiments. This framework was based on a merger between statistical and SE process concepts, including explicit roles.

- The high-level conceptual model (see this link) could be endorsed by any experimenter (with some complaints depending on their specialization area, as it happened during the ethnography). However, when the concept of a role appears in the scene, the high-level model is just an abstraction of the information handled by the roles. In other words, the high-level model is incomplete from the roles' viewpoint and thus partially valid. The high-level model evokes the viewpoint of the *SrEx* (see this link), but with fewer details. In turn, the EM (see this link) and the RM (see this link) pay little attention to the design and execution details because the *senior experimenter* takes care of that. Likewise, the EM is not affected by the experimental research in its global context, e.g., collaboration with other groups and replication. Such a concern fits the RM's role.
- We deliberately built the models (process, workflow, and conceptual) to offer a coherent picture. However, as we indicated in Section 3.3.3, we were unable to address the existence of different families of experiments. When experimenters working in other families get together, the models automatically diverge. Therefore, the models represent the maximum achievable consensus obtained during the role-oriented meetings. We are conscious that further research is necessary at the family level to discover the peculiarities of each research area. Such an inquiry could have an impact on the SE community.
- The replication problem is related to knowledge transfer [53, 54]. Nevertheless, we wonder what exactly it means to transfer knowledge? To what extent or how should it be done? For example, Ferreira et al. [55] emphasize methodological consistency over discussing methods and techniques. There appears to be an underlying dichotomy between theory and practice. In theory, formal guides, such as replication packages, should clearly describe the process. However, the practice shows that such mechanisms cannot cope with the existing diversity of experimental protocols. The replication process will likely benefit from the specialized, fine-grained knowledge at the family level.

The models (process, workflow, and conceptual) and the ethnographic experience have generated some SE experimental process's differential characteristics or viewpoints, e.g., context adaptation and iterative improvement. Previous research pointed out some of these characteristics, e.g., [52, 53, 56]. We do not wish to provide a detailed account of these differential characteristics herein; that would require a publication of a different character. Instead, we aimed to observe how experimenters work and found out that they perform tasks other than those portrayed in textbooks. This is our essential contribution.

We also know that models represent the point of view of a single experimental research group. We must extend the inquiry to other experimental research groups, ideally to a large portion of the ESE community, and verify whether they reveal similar behavior patterns.

It is worth noting that, while incidents were collected only from a single research group, the observed divergences among roles may reflect broader behavioral tendencies present in similar research environments. This ethnographic focus prioritizes depth and contextual richness over breadth, which is consistent with interpretive research paradigms. Nevertheless, future work may consider comparative analysis across multiple research groups to enhance external validity.

6. Threats to Validity

Validity refers to the degree to which the research is conducted transparently and without bias. We have followed Runeson et al.'s recommendations [23, pp. 71–73] to design the ethnographic research and describe the threats to validity. Runeson et al., following Yin [57], classify threats into four groups: (1) construct validity, (2) internal validity, (3) external validity, and (4) reliability.

6.1. Construct Validity. Construct validity deals with the degree of agreement between the study constructs, i.e., what the ethnographic researchers have in mind, and the observations made in the field. For example, if the interview questions are not interpreted the same way by the researcher and the experimenters, there is a threat to construct validity.

The ethnographic method is particularly suitable to oppose this threat because knowledge acquisition progresses gradually. Additionally, we employed several techniques during the research to create constructs, including reading, observation, and interviews, among others. The different approaches increase the chances of identifying or solving misunderstandings between the researchers and the RGUS. Using reliable information sources, such as standard literature and the RGUS' experimental material, we also addressed construct validity threats.

Finally, the constructs were validated iteratively by experimenters and researchers throughout the lifespan of the research project.

6.2. Internal Validity. Internal validity addresses the credibility of the causal relationships found during the research. However, this threat does not apply to this ethnographic study, as we do not aim to identify causal relationships but, at most, correlations between phenomena, e.g., when we claim that the number and diversity of experimental tasks explain the existence of roles. Furthermore, most of the findings we provide are descriptive, for example, disagreements among experimenters from different experimental families.

6.3. External Validity. External validity represents the degree of certainty that the findings obtained in an investigation are generalizable, i.e., applicable to different contexts of their origin. This threat is prominent in this study since it was carried out in a single instance (an experimental research group) of the population under study (SE research groups that apply

empirical methods). As a countermeasure, we chose a highly representative experimental research group.

6.4. Reliability. The reliability of a study is the ease with which the research activities and the results obtained can be reproduced by other studies that apply the same methodology in the same RGUS (more likely, in similar experimental research groups).

To ensure the reliability of this research, we have closely followed the research methodology outlined in Section 2. Moreover, we have disclosed all intermediate and final results in a repository available upon request to guarantee transparency in the investigation.

7. Conclusions

Experimental researchers know that experimentation, as described in textbooks and articles, only approximates the daily work in the lab and the field. This study shows the deviations found in a concrete experimental research group. Such divergences do not seem arbitrary but are necessary from a systemic viewpoint; for example, people have distinct abilities and perform different tasks in a research project.

We do not claim that our findings are commonplace in the empirical community. They may be particular to the experimental research group where we performed the ethnographic study. However, some clues evidence that peculiar behaviors are usual in the lab and the field. For instance, researchers in the natural sciences have complained about the replication problem [58]. At least in the sciences (maybe not in SE), replication frequently fails due to experimental setup and conduction changes. These changes are motivated by the researchers' tacit knowledge [38, 59], and consequently, protocols or experiment reports do not declare such changes. Experiment variations happen so frequently that some disciplines have coined a (comic) term: "lab mythology" [60, 61]. Our study has shown that such tacit knowledge is present in SE and manifests superficially, e.g., when researchers from different experimental families discuss their mental models.

Furthermore, anecdotal evidence, such as conversations with colleagues, suggests that this "lab mythology" may also be somewhat present in SE. We all know that experimental reports do not always accurately reflect the experimental process. It does not mean experimenters cheat. We all know from experience that some practices are effective and others are not, and we apply them as needed.

7.1. Implications for Practice. Our findings suggest specific improvements that could be applied to SE experimentation. The first and most evident is transitioning from an experimental process primarily based on the application of experimental designs and the conduct of statistical analyses to a more professional approach based on explicit processes, activities, and roles, as is customary in many areas, e.g., Information Technology [62].

It could be argued that current SE experimentation already has a well-defined process and activities, as can be seen, e.g., in the works of Juristo and Moreno [33] or Wohlin et al. [32]. However, as we have argued before, such a process and

activities represent only an idealization of the activities performed in practice. We refer to more detailed processes and activities (such as the process models we provide in this work).

Detailed processes and activities only make sense within specific research areas or even families of experiments. For example, Arcuri and Briand [63] have published recommendations for the statistical analysis of randomized algorithms. Arcuri & Briand do not claim that their recommendations have general applicability. Other areas of SE, such as programming or testing, will need specific recommendations. Although this may seem strange or unusual, a cursory examination of experimental literature in other sciences reveals the opposite. For example, in Psychology, there are recommendations on how to measure motivation [64] or consider experience [65]. In Medicine, there are models of pain [66]. Other examples could be cited, but all of them agree on highlighting the specificities of a research area instead of hiding details in abstractions that ultimately prove inoperative.

Finally, we must add specific competencies to processes, activities, and roles, such as negotiation skills, asset curation, or human resource management. Again, SE is lagging behind established trends in other areas. To cite a very relevant example, the European Union [67] has defined a framework containing seven competency areas, 38 competencies, and 389 learning outcomes for researchers. Other institutions have undertaken similar efforts.

7.2. Limitations. However, this work is subject to various limitations. The first and most important is the empirical basis obtained. Although ethnographic research has been extensive over time and conducted using multiple techniques, we ultimately have data from only one research group. Furthermore, this group’s experimenters have self-trained in the field, meaning they have not received specific academic training. The observed peculiarities could be habits acquired over time that other, more recent groups with formal training do not possess.

We also cannot rule out errors in perception on the researchers’ part as well. As mentioned earlier, we had yet to learn of experimentation at the beginning of ethnographic research, which may have led us to misinterpret some behaviors of the experimenters. On the other hand, perhaps the researchers’ “fresh” perspective has allowed us to identify our findings.

In addition, we acknowledge that this study relied exclusively on qualitative ethnographic methods, without complementary quantitative analyses. While this was deliberate to capture tacit and contextual aspects in depth, it also limits the possibility of statistical validation of the findings. Future work, therefore, will explicitly combine these qualitative insights with quantitative approaches (e.g., surveys, statistical models) to enhance verification and generalizability.

7.3. Future Work. To overcome the limitations of the present investigation, it is necessary to carry out further studies to generalize the results of the current work. Our plans are as follows:

- Verify the existence of terminological diversity, one of the first aspects that has emerged in the research and is relatively easy to check. We have already started this

work. We surveyed SE experimenters from multiple research groups. In the survey, we asked them about the meaning and usage of experimentation-related terms. Preliminary results confirm the existence of terminological diversity.

- After completing the ethnographic research, we initiated a comparative study of the experimental process between SE and an established engineering discipline (specifically, biotechnology). Preliminary results indicate the absence of terminological diversity and a greater formalization of the experimental process within specific research areas, but not at a general level. This could be the key to terminological diversity in SE: subareas of SE generally have not developed specific terminology and protocols, which could lead to the need for ad-hoc concepts and processes.

Both works will likely be published shortly. In addition, we plan to conduct more studies in the future on this topic. We still need to decide on the objects under study and the methodologies used, since ethnography is very demanding. A possibility to study the impact of specialization in the sciences is to analyze experimental repositories. This represents an indirect but efficient approach in terms of time and effort. Another alternative is conducting qualitative studies using focus groups composed of SE experimental researchers.

Appendix A: Acronyms

TABLE A1: Acronyms used throughout the manuscript.

Acronym	Term
EM	Experiment manager
EPM	Experimental process model
EPW	Experimental process workflow
ESE	Empirical software engineering
RGUS	Research group under study
RM	Research manager
SE	Software engineering
SrEx	Senior experimenter

Data Availability Statement

The data supporting the findings of this study are partially available through the open-access repositories cited throughout the manuscript (e.g., Zenodo records containing anonymized excerpts and supporting materials). Due to privacy and ethical considerations related to the ethnographic nature of the research, some datasets that include identifiable or sensitive information cannot be shared publicly. However, additional data may be made available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request, provided that it is in accordance with institutional data protection policies.

Disclosure

All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript. This work’s preprint has been published [68].

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Author Contributions

The authors confirm contributions to the manuscript as follows: Efraín R. Fonseca C. led the conceptualization of the study, research design, ethnographic data collection, data analysis, and preparation of the original draft. Marta López-Fernández contributed to the methodological framework, validation of findings, and writing, as well as review and editing. Oscar Dieste provided guidance on study design, contributed to data interpretation, and participated in critical revision of the manuscript. Natalia Juristo supervised the research, ensured methodological rigor, and contributed to project administration and final approval of the manuscript.

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Endnotes

¹The acronyms used throughout the paper are listed in Table A1 in the appendix.

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